

DTERBIM News

Insights on digital, circular and energy-efficient construction and renovation

N° 1: 19 December 2025

Dear reader,

Welcome to the DTERBIM community! We're glad to have you here.

Did you know that buildings use around 40% of Europe's energy and generate over a third of its waste, mostly from construction and demolition? Yet roughly 75% of Europe's building stock is still energy inefficient.

This sector is central to the EU's climate and energy goals, but it faces major challenges: limited digitalisation, fragmented tools, difficulties applying circular and sustainability principles, and skills gaps that slow innovation.

That's where DTERBIM (Driving Transformation on Energy-efficient and Circular Renovation through BIM) comes in. **We're improving how buildings are designed, renovated, and managed by shifting from linear, fragmented processes to open, collaborative, circular workflows.** By combining BIM, AI, and Digital Twins within an openBIM ecosystem, we enable better decision-making and more efficient resource use across the full building lifecycle.

In this first edition, you'll find a snapshot of our **early milestones**: the launch of our new website, our official kick-off meeting in Spain, our first press release, and an introduction to our team. We've also gathered **useful insights, opportunities, and resources** from across the sector.

Let's get started!

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Main story: [**Our new website is live**](#)

We're excited to announce that **DTERBIM's brand-new website is now online!**

It's your go-to hub for everything DTERBIM: our mission, vision, pilots, partners, EU synergies, public resources, updates, and the tools we're developing to make construction and renovation smarter, greener, and more circular.

Explore our BIM-based methodology and toolkit, discover our virtual and real-life pilots in Spain, Poland, and Greece, and meet the team making it all happen.

[Visit the website](#)

Official kick-off in Spain

On 29–30 October 2025, representatives from all DTERBIM partner organisations gathered in Valladolid, Spain, for our **official kick-off, hosted by our coordinator, CARTIF.**

Over two days, we aligned on goals, mapped out next steps, and visited one of our real-world pilot buildings, offering a first glimpse of how our work will translate into practice.

This meeting marked the start of our **42-month collaboration** to turn openBIM, Digital Twins, and smart tools into practical solutions for renovation projects across Europe.

[Learn more](#) →

[Our first press release is out](#)

Our launch press release outlines DTERBIM's goals, approach, and expected impact. It introduces our methodology and the pilot demonstrations that will test it in real conditions.

“The DTERBIM project aims to demonstrate how digitalisation can transform the way we design, renovate, and manage buildings, integrating circularity for a more efficient and sustainable process.”

Ultimately, DTERBIM aspires to take a decisive step toward a more innovative, circular, and connected architecture, engineering and construction (AEC) sector.”

— Sonia Álvarez Díaz, DTERBIM Coordinator.

[Read the press release](#) →

[Meet the DTERBIM team](#)

DTERBIM brings together **18 partners** from **8 countries**, covering every stage of the building lifecycle.

From construction firms and architects to software providers, researchers, and policy and communication experts, we combine expertise to drive circular, data-driven renovation.

We're introducing each partner through a **social media campaign**. Join the conversation on [LinkedIn](#), [Bluesky](#), and [X](#) to check out what they bring to DTERBIM.

[Meet our partners](#) →

Fresh news from the sector

Article: [LIFE showcases sustainable construction and renovation at Building Green 2025](#)

Publication: [Policy packages for a socially just renovation of residential buildings](#)

Given Europe's pressing need for low-impact, scalable construction, Building Green 2025 was a great opportunity for LIFE projects to share a range of sustainable solutions for both new-build

developments and the renovation of existing structures.

This report explores how policy packages can be designed to address the worst-performing buildings and protect vulnerable households, ensuring that the transition is fair and inclusive.

Event: [European Energy Efficiency Conference 2026](#)

Energy efficiency = energy independence. This is the motto of this conference, taking place on **25–27 February** in Wels, Austria. It will present policies, technologies and business models which increase competitiveness and make energy more affordable.

Podcast: [The Construction Revolution Podcast](#)

This Podcast explores the latest technologies, individuals, companies and business practices that are revolutionising the construction industry. [Its latest episode](#) explores how real-time aggregate data is changing the way concrete is optimised.

As 2025 comes to a close, we'd like to **thank you for your interest and support**. We hope the coming weeks give you time to slow down and recharge.

In our next newsletters, we'll share more project updates, partner stories, and insights from across Europe's construction and renovation sector, all focused on circularity, energy efficiency, and smarter building practices.

Thanks for reading,
The DTERBIM Team

Get in touch

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101235920. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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